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The Impacts of Oil Spill Disaster on Communities and its Influence on Restiveness in Niger Delta, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is the sixth-largest exporter of oil and correspondingly the sixth largest nation among the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). The petroleum product account for more than 90% foreign exchange for the Federation of Nigeria while the immediate environment suffers more than 90% environment and socio-economic degeneration. From 2004 to 2011 excluding minor leakages from 'tapped' joints from illegal bunkering, oil spills recorded in the area was over 110 bbl affecting over 10 ha of land, some of which have been remediated. No data of spill is available until recently when three spills (Odeama Well 9, Santa Barbra Well 1 and NCTL at Botokiri) occurred resulting in the release of 1464.5 bbl into the environment. Which is the subject of this study. The incidences of oil spills however, negatively impacted the Niger Delta communities and the environment described as one among the worst impacted zones globally. Whilst the affected communities struggle for attention and justice for the environmental damages through protest, agitations and violence, the Nigerian state and the oil and gas industries continue with their operations. The paper investigates impact of the oil spills on community's livelihood structures and its influence on restiveness in selected Niger delta affected communities. The paper adopts a qualitative research through interviews and group discussions with social activist, chiefs, experts in the field, youths and community leaders to identify oil spill impacts on community socio-economic conditions. Data collected were analyzed using thematic template analytic techniques. The study shows a high impact on the entire communities with different factors that have contributed to the increase on social aspects of the affected. The paper makes a recommendation to all stakeholders within oil related and the multinationals to improve their strategies and or contingency planning in tackling oil spill-related issues and adhere to community's plight when appropriate.

Keywords: Technological Disaster; Oil Spill; Socio-economic; Niger- Delta-Nigeria; Restiveness; Community

1. INTRODUCTION

On 1st October 2019, about 116 bbl of crude oil spilled from Santa Barbra well I and the JIV indicated that the cause of the spill was sabotage. A second spill was reported on 31st October 2019 at NCTL in Botokiri community, filling about 1300 bbl of crude oil and the cause of the spill was equipment failure. A third spill occurred on the 11th of May 2020 releasing about 48.5 bbl of crude oil which was allegedly due to corrosion. While most countries of the world faced natural hazards, Nigeria is faced with numerous technological and or human induced hazards, among which oil spills are leading with severe short and long term cumulative impacts on affected populace. For instance, European nation experienced 10

incidences of oil spills in 40 years, while Nigeria experienced 9,343 incidences in 10 years [1, 2]. Studies have also shown that the quantity of oil spilled in the Nigerian environment in five decades was at least 9-13million barrels, equivalent to (50) Exxon Valdez oil spills of 1989 (260,000 barrels) [3, 4]. This positioned the region as one among five most ruthlessly petroleum damaged environment in the world [5, 6]. Consequently, these disasters have affected the environment, arable lands, water resources and livelihood structures of the immediate oil producing communities of Nigeria [5]. The impact further degenerates to increase in poverty, crisis and unrest within the crude oil producing environment [7]. Leading to formulations of different agitation groups in call for environmental justice and livelihood support mechanisms. This paper stresses, that oil spills have not just caused environmental, ecological, water and air pollution, but have negative stark socioeconomic breakdown which includes loss of job and restiveness through the non-payment of monetary and infrastructural compensations to affected host and transit oil communities. This calls for the need to investigate the socio-economic impacts specifically, as large number of studies have looked at the environmental and health impacts [8-12]. Importantly, how the impact influence restiveness using statistical analytical tools for the analysis.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Disasters and Disaster Impacts

The term 'Disaster' has undergone a number of efforts at redefining, with some more effective than others, depending on the purpose and interest, what individuals consider as a disaster, the situation, disciplines and context. Quarantelli and Dynes [13], described disaster as an entrance into a state of uncertainty, duplication of war, catastrophe and, an expression of social vulnerabilities. Mohamed Shaluf [14], described disasters as an emergency occurring due to human-induced or natural hazards that result in noteworthy changes in circumstances over a period. However, this definition doesn't reflect the harshness of the incidents. Parker and Handmer [15] define disaster as "unusual natural or man-made event, including an event caused by failure of technological systems, which temporarily crushes the response capacity of human communities, groups of individuals or natural environment and which causes massive damage, economic loss, disruption, injury and/ or loss of life". However, United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction [16] describe disaster "as a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or society, involving widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses and impacts, which exceeding the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resource" (p.9). This definition embodies the same as Parker and Handmer [15] emphasis on the economic and human ability to withstand the harshness of the effects. From the definition above, disaster can be defined as an un-prevented incident that forcefully placed vulnerable people in the quest for external assistance and this study adopts the definition of the United Nations.

2.2 Disaster Impacts

The strictness of any incident is not the volume and magnitude but the effects [17]. The most necessary factor in determining the seriousness of an incident such as oil spill, is where the oil ends. The extent of the effect, weather condition, socio-economic characteristic of the location and the communities therein. These in a way can be influenced by the 'developed or developing' nations and the response techniques, clean-up measures adopted, the effectiveness and the environmental benefit. Hence, both developed and developing nations suffers oil spill incidents [18]. For example, the 2010 Gulf of Mexico oil spill and Exxon Valdez oil spill of 1989 affected thousands of sea birds, fishes, fishing industries and waterways with continuous impact on communities [19, 20]. On the contrary, developing countries such as Angola and Nigeria are faced with similar and or worst scenarios of incidents of oil spills with degenerating impacts due to lack of management measures, response strategies and policy enforcement. Hence, it's evident that disaster can occur anywhere, but frequently, the poor and underdeveloped countries who suffers the most severe and long-term impacts. For instance, there are growing anxieties regarding threats on loss of biodiversity, deforestation and environmental pollution [21], in the Nigerian context. Different habitats have trailed their biodiversity at an unexpected proportion [21-23], aquatic species and wildlife have been reported depleting and threat on plant species extinction [6]. The impacts on the environment remains disheartening as the environment is a man's first right and foundation for

other rights [24]. These also increase the concerns for environmental justices and pollution control campaign for drawing the world attention towards the reduction means of the degenerating impacts of oil spills on the societies. Nwilo and Badejo [25] mentioned specifically, on the degenerating situations of the Nigerian oil-producing environment with emphasis on mismanagement and lack of environmental regulation enforcement as a key drawback for proper environmental management systems. Kadafa [5] further argued that oil spill impacts on the environment and ecosystem services have increased poverty rate and displacement of people physically, mentally and job wise. The arguments of Kadafa [5]; and Nwilo and Badejo [25], demonstrate significantly, how oil spill have impacted on the environment and the ecology with the degenerated negative impacts on the social aspect of the communities which cut across local economic growth and restiveness. “These issues have received little attention so far”

2.2.1 *Social and Economic impacts of oil spill disaster*

Social impacts are the changes made by an organisation or company through their activities which affects the economic and wellbeing of the populace. Hence, Pegg and Zabbey [22]; Fentiman and Zabbey [24] and Celestine [26] in their different studies emphasise the severity of oil spills not just on the environment but also on culture, traditions, local economic, norms, values and ways of life among communities. However, Ebegbulem, Ekpe [7] points that oil spillages in the unique Niger Delta states have caused extensive social underdevelopment which engrosses lack of social amenities, physical infrastructure, piped water, schools, hospitals, and employment opportunities, despite the huge benefit of the crude oil product with or without oil spills on the Nigerian national economy [7]. The above argument demonstrates that instead of an increase in social and economic conditions through contributions from the end-product of the crude oil. The reverse is the case, as loss of sources of livelihood from the disaster has caused great unemployment. Further, Okonkwo [27], points that most social impacts of oil spill covers violence and frustrations, reduction in tourism and hospitality industries. Okonkwo’s points are similar to Gill, Picou [28], who revealed how the British Petroleum (BP) oil spill and Exxon Valdez oil spill caused several social impacts, threatening several ‘at risk’ including industries, commercial and recreational fishing, tourism and other enterprises tied to their natural resources. The arguments draw the importance to establish that oil spill disaster directly and indirectly affects societies and communities in various dimensions.

2.2.2 *Table Showing commonly faced impacts*

The table below highlights some impacts commonly faced as a results of petroleum production within affected Niger Delta communities. These impacts on the environment have led to dissatisfaction on the communities, hence, leading to degradation of human development. Chukwuemeka and Aghara [29], adds that the dissatisfaction of affected communities is on the level of damages to the ecology by several oil spills, marginalisation and neglects regarding the development of the region. However, Chukwuemeka and Aghara [29] study did not employ any statistical and or content analytical tool for analysis. Hence, emphasises the severity of the impacts.

Table 1. The Direct and Indirect Impacts of oil spills

<i>Direct impacts of oil spills</i>	<i>Indirect impacts of oil spills</i>
<i>Environment, air, water pollution, loss of biodiversity, deforestation, displacement, loss of jobs, acid rain, skin irritation,</i>	<i>Ingestion of contaminated food, violent conflicts, frustration, prostitution, agitations, depletion of wildlife, aquatic and plants</i>

3. **STUDY METHODOLOGY**

The study assesses oil spill impacts on livelihood structures and how it influenced restiveness within affected Niger Delta communities of Nigeria. Qualitative research design is adopted using different techniques such as; focus group discussion, interviews, documents and secondary data. Eleven (11) key members of communities were purposively selected for an in-depth interview discussion in their various communities. Focus group discussion were conducted within the selected areas of the study. The participants include; youth leaders, members of periwinkle company association, chiefs, members of

community representatives and members of social activists group. The rationale for selecting them was that these key people are indigenous and have lived all their lives within the communities. The participants also possess the relevant experiences for the research question under investigation, having lived and experienced different kinds of oil spills and operations of the oil and gas industries within the boundaries and shores of the region.

3.1 Field Sampling Activities

Field sampling activities commenced from 30/11/2022 - 15/03/2023 and laboratory analysis followed thereafter. Sampling involved collection of samples from the various environmental matrices including surface water, sediment, groundwater, soil, vegetation, plankton, benthos and fisheries. A total of Three Hundred and Eighty-Four (384) samples of soil, sediment, surface water, plankton, benthos and vegetation were collected. Socioeconomic and health studies were also carried out through interviews, questionnaire administration, literature and walk-through surveys.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Crude Oil Characterization and Fingerprinting

The chemical fingerprinting analyses of the reference crude oil taken from Santa Barbara Well-1, were compared with oil extracted from the alleged contaminated soil samples from the four communities, namely Owukubu, Amgbakiri, Shellkiri and Diepreye. The diagnostic ratios recorded for the samples were compared to those of reference oil with the sole aim of determining the source of the spilled crude oil. Results show that the oil extracted from these communities were similar to the reference oil except that of Shellkiri that was of a different origin.

4.2 Climate and Meteorology

Climate and meteorological parameters including rainfall and humidity, sunlight radiation and temperature, wind speed, turbulence and direction etc., influence the impact and fate of oil spills. The study area lies within the humid tropical zone with defined dry (November- March) and wet (April - October) seasons. The wet season is brought about by the South-West trade wind blowing across the Atlantic Ocean. This begins around April and stretches to October. September and October are the peak months of flood in the area. The Hood gradually recedes from November. The dry, dusty and often cold North-East trade winds blowing across the Sahara Desert dominates the dry season and brings a short period of harmattan. This starts around November and terminates in March. In general, the weather regime in the area is determined primarily by geographical location in relation to the fluctuating position of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone.

4.3 Surface Water

Odeama Well-9

Surface water reaction values varied with sampling points. Its pH values ranged from 6.77 to 7.42, with an average value of 7.18. These values fall within the FMEnv set maximum allowable limit of 40.00mg/l for surface water. Also, salinity (determined as chloride) ranged between 2419.00mg/l and 7705.00mg/l with an average value of 4060.13mg/l- indicating the water bodies in this area are brackish as the chloride levels across the sample stations exceeded 2000mg/l. The dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand and chemical oxygen demand values recorded mean values of 5.64mg/l, 5.91 mg/l and 15.93mg/l respectively. Total suspended solids' concentrations varied from 20.00mg/l - 440.00mg/l with mean value of 138.75mg/l, which is higher than the FMEnv set limit of 40.00mg/l for surface water bodies in Nigeria. The water bodies recorded low concentration levels of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH) across the study area with values ranging from 0.22mg/l to 18.58mg/l with a mean value of 2.63mg/l, except at two points close to the spill point, SW1 - 18.58mg/l and SW2 10.55mg/l. Polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon and BTEX were below the detection limit (0.00mg/l) of the analytical instruments. Heavy metal ions were obtained in traces and compare favourably with the control sample with mean levels of 0.93mg/l and 0.13mg/l for Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Zn^{2+} respectively. Other metals (Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , V^{2+} , and Ba^{2+}) were below their respective detection limits. Cd^{2+} and Ni^{2+} had concentration lower than the regulatory limits. Total heterotrophic bacteria and total fungi were of mean population loads of 1.77×10^4 cfu/ml and 1.07×10^4 cfu/ml respectively. The HUB and HUF loads were low, indicating low petroleum hydrocarbon level in

the surface water matrix and vis a vis effective degradation of petroleum hydrocarbon in the water bodies of the oil contaminated area.

Santa Barbara Well-1

The water bodies at and surrounding vicinity of Santa Barbara well-1 were fairly acidic with pH values ranging from 6.2 - 6.8 (mean value = 6.5). The dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) mean values were 5.69mg/l, 6.44mg/l and 13.14mg/l respectively. Total Suspended Solids varied from 20.00mg/l - 320.00mg/l with mean concentration of 163.33mg/l - a value which exceeded 40mg/l maximum limit set for an aquatic environment. Exchangeable cations recorded mean value of 244.86mg/l, 83.85mg/l, 161.66mg/l and 1188.35mg/l for Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺ and Na⁺ respectively. Furthermore, TPH concentration levels varied between 0.52mg/l and 25.67mg/l, the highest recorded value at sampled point closest to the spill point. Polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon and BTEX were below the detection limit (0.001mg/l) of the analytical instruments and could be said to be absent in these water bodies.

Heavy metal ions were also obtained in traces and compare favorably with the control sample with mean levels of 0.72mg/l and 0.09mg/l for Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Zn²⁺ respectively. Other metals (Ni²⁺, Hg²⁺, V²⁺, and Ba²⁺) were below their respective detection limits. Total heterotrophic bacteria load ranged from 1.35 - 4.00 x 10⁴ cfu/ml with an average value of 2.26 x 10⁴ cfu/ml while total fungi load ranged from 1.00 - 1.95 x 10⁴ cfu/ml with an average population load of 1.33 x 10⁴ cfu/ml.

ES 3.0: 24" NCTL Row at Botokiri

The pH values of the surface water along the pipeline right of way ranged from 6.1 - 7.6 with an average value of 7.1. The BODs and COD mean values were 6.20mg/l and 13.65mg/l respectively while dissolved oxygen levels ranged from 5.00 - 6.00mg/l with a mean value of 5.63mg/l. Exchangeable cations recorded mean value of 244.86mg/l, 83.85mg/l, 161.66mg/l and 1188.35mg/l for Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺ and Na⁺ respectively. Also, total petroleum hydrocarbon levels ranged from 0.22mg/l to 12.58mg/l (mean = 1.78mg/l) while Polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon (PAHs) and BTEX were below the detection limit (0.001mg/l) of the laboratory analytical instruments. Heavy metal ions were also obtained in traces and compared favourably with the control sample, with mean levels of 0.66mg/l and 0.11mg/l for Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Zn²⁺ respectively. Other metals (Ni²⁺, Hg²⁺, V²⁺, and Ba²⁺) were below their respective detection limits. Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ had concentrations lower than the regulatory limits. Total heterotrophic bacteria load ranged from 1.03 - 2.90 x 10⁴ cfu/ml with an average value of 1.67 x 10⁴ cfu/ml while total fungi load ranged from 1.00 - 1.25 x 10⁴ cfu/ml with an average population load of 1.04 x 10⁴ cfu/ml.

GROUNDWATER QUALITY

Groundwater potability tests were carried out on the borehole water samples collected from Okioku Twemi, Owukubu and Ikensi communities. The pH of the groundwater ranged from 6.4- 7.6 (mean = 6.9). The mean pH value of 6.9 indicates that the groundwater from the region is within the WHO / FMEnv permissible values of 6.5-8.5 for drinking water. The conductivities ranged from 95.40gS/cm - 1066 pS/cm with a mean value of 461.44pS/cm. Similarly, total dissolved solids varied from 50.56mg/l to 564.98mg/l with a mean value of 244.56mg/l. The dissolved oxygen, TSS, COD and Salinity varied from 4.50mg/l - 5.10mg/l, 40.00mg/l - 240.00mg/l (mean = 136.00mg/l), 7.90mg/l - 9.15mg/l (mean=8.49mg/l) and 8.83mg/l - 318.00mg/l (mean = 105.92mg/l) respectively. The TPH, BTEX and PAHs level were below the analytical instruments' detection limit of 0.001mg/l. Hence there was no petroleum hydrocarbon contamination of the groundwater.

SEDIMENT

Odeama Well- 9 Spill Site-

Sediment acidity ranged between pH values of 2.7 and 6.3, with a mean value of 4.2. The inorganic nutrients were in moderate concentrations sufficient to support aquatic plants and benthic organisms. The anions namely; sulphate, nitrate and phosphate were in mean concentration levels of 161.88mg/kg, 9.85mg/kg and 2.13mg/kg respectively. Total petroleum hydrocarbon levels varied from 15.48mg/kg at Okpokiri community to 2512mg/kg at the spill site. Relatively high levels of petroleum hydrocarbon were recorded in the sediment sample collected from close vicinity of the spill site, but were below the intervention value (5000mg/kg). BTEX was practically absent (<0.001mg/kg) across all the sampling

stations, including the affected communities while PAHs ranged from <0.01mg/kg - 0.02mg/kg. The PAHs concentration levels were far below the set Target value of 1.0mg/kg for soil and sediment. Heavy metals' concentrations were below their respective DPR intervention values and are also comparable with the control values. Microbiological analysis revealed that total heterotrophic bacteria loads ranged from 1.40- 3.55 x 10⁴cfu/g with an average value of 2.30 x 10⁴cfu/g while total fungi load ranged from 1.15- 1.34 x 10⁴ cfii/g with an average population load of 1.34 x10⁴ cfu/g. These microbial loads compare favorably with population loads recorded at the control points.

Santa Barbara Well -1

The sediment samples were acidic across the sampling stations, including the control point. Its values ranged from 3.1 - 6.0 with an average value of 4.5. Total organic carbon and total nitrogen contents were of mean values of 0.74% and 1.28% respectively. Also, nitrate ranged from 0.86mg/kg - 18.12mg/kg, phosphate; 0.72mg/kg - 4.62mg/kg while sulphate varied from 173mg/kg - 278.00mg/kg. Total petroleum hydrocarbon and PAHs were recorded in concentrations range of 1.57mg/kg (Twini community) - 1523mg/kg (Spill Point) with a mean value of 413.09mg/kg and 0.02mg/kg-0.85mg/kg (mean = 0.74mg/kg) respectively. BTEX were, however, below the detection limit (0.001 mg/kg) of the analytical equipment. TPH and PAHs were obtained in concentration levels below their intervention values. Heavy metals' levels (mg/kg) were in mean values of 17437, 47.38, 23.14, 18.63, 1.04, 15.48, and 13.38 for Iron, Zinc, Chromium, Lead, Cadmium, Nickel and Copper respectively. However, Barium, Arsenic, Vanadium and Mercury were practically absent in the sediment across all the sample stations, even as other metals' concentrations were below the respective Intervention values. Microbiological analysis revealed that THE, TF, HUB and HUF were in average population loads of 2.20 x10⁴cfu/g, 1.41 x10⁴cfu/g, 1.01 x10²cfii/g and 0.67 x10² cfu/g respectively. Hydrocarbon utilizers are considered present in moderate population loads capable of further degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons in the bottom sediment across the study area.

24" NCTL Sediment Properties

The pH values of the sediment and control stations were within acidic scale, with values ranging from 2.2- 5.3. The percent total organic carbon ranged from 0.62% - 1.40% with a mean value of 0.95%. Nitrate ranged from 2.16mg/kg to 32.79mg/kg while phosphate levels varied from 0.46mg/kg - 5.13mg/kg with a mean value of 2.20mg/kg. Total petroleum hydrocarbon levels were low across the study area, including the communities, with values ranging from 10.06mg/kg to 154.20mg/kg. Lowest concentration (10.06mg/kg) of TPH was recorded in sediment taken from Dasaba community while Borokiri and Seriakiri had 125.80mg/kg and 10.27mg/kg respectively. The recorded TPH levels in sediment samples with the spill impact zone were, summarily, far below its set Intervention limit of 5000mg/kg. The BTEX and PAHs were practically absent across the sampling station. The most abundant metal was Fe with concentration levels ranging from 12690 mg/kg -22150mg/kg, followed by Zinc (16.80mg/kg -40.20mg/kg); Chromium (7.40mg/kg -14.80mg/kg), Lead (7.70mg/kg -13.80 mg/kg); Nickel (3.80-8.70mg/kg) and Copper (2.20mg/kg) and Nickel (Ni) 3.80mg/kg - 7.40 mg/kg). Recorded concentrations of heavy metals in the sediment samples taken across the study area were below their respective intervention values. Microbiological examination of sediment revealed TUB population loads that ranged from 2.00- 4.00 x 10⁴ cfu/g, with an average population load of 2.91 x 10⁴ cfu/g while TF ranged from 1.00- 3.00 x 10¹ cfu/g with a mean value of 1.80 x 10⁴cfu/g. Presence of hydrocarbon degraders (HUB and HUF) in sediment shows possibility of further biodegradation process of petroleum hydrocarbon in the study area.

SOIL

Odeama Well-9 Oil spill

The pH of the soil varied from strongly acidic to alkaline with values that ranged from 2.5-8.3 for the topsoil and 2.4 - 7.7 for bottom soil. Total organic carbon and total nitrogen levels varied from 0.06- 1.26% and 0.02-1.75% respectively in the topsoil and from 0.01-1.36% and 0.02-2.39% respectively in the bottom soil. Furthermore, inorganic soil nutrients in topsoil recorded average concentrations levels of 201.85mg/kg for sulphate, 28.66mg/kg for nitrate and 1.73mg/kg for phosphate while the bottom soil had 186.27mg/kg, 23.41mg/kg and 2.94mg/kg respectively. The topsoil and bottom soil recorded total

petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) which ranged from 15.48mg/kg and 4804mg/kg and 19.76mg/kg to 5922mg/kg respectively, while polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) concentrations ranged from 0.02mg/kg - 1.20mg/kg in the topsoil and 0.15mg/kg - 1.80mg/kg in the bottom soil. The levels of BTEX across the sample stations were below the equipment detection limit of <0.01 mg/kg. Total hydrocarbon concentrations in the topsoil and bottom soil at each of the sample stations were below the Intervention value of 5000mg/kg. Heavy metals levels in the topsoil ranged from 7520 mg/kg -28120mg/kg, 3.20 mg/kg - 66.00mg/kg, 6.70 mg/kg - 34.40mg/kg, 0.10 mg/kg-1.10mg/kg, <0.001-0.60mg/kg, 2.20mg/kg - 34.90mg/kg and 4.70mg/kg-33.80mg/kg for Fe, Zn, Cr, Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu respectively. Similarly, bottom soil contained metals in various concentrations ranging from 8970-19340mg/kg for Fe, 9.40-61.20mg/kg for Zn, 3.20-33.60mg/kg for Cr, 1.60 mg/kg-18.50mg/kg, 0.10 mg/kg- 1.50mg/kg, 2.40mg/kg - 32.20mg/kg for Ni and 2.50 mg/kg - 31.80mg/kg for Cu. However, Mercury (Hg), Barium (Ba) and Arsenic (As) levels were below the detection limit (0.001mg/kg)

of the analytical equipment. All metals were in concentrations far below their respective Intervention values across the sample stations indicating that the spill site and even the affected communities' soils were not polluted with heavy metals resulting from the spill incident. Microbiological analysis revealed moderate population densities of the total heterotrophic bacteria (THB), total fungi (TF), Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria, and Hydrocarbon Utilizing Fungi. Presence of hydrocarbon utilizers in the study area reflects continuous degradation process and in turn cleansing of petroleum hydrocarbon in the affected oil spill soil strata.

Santa Barbara Well -1 Oil spill

The pH values of the topsoil in the hydrocarbon contaminated area varied between 2.08 and 6.80 with a mean level of 4.45 showing a slightly acidic property of the soils. This value was slightly higher than the pH of the soil from the control area which was 4.19. Extremely acidic conditions were recorded in the topsoil near the spill site and at the Amgbakiri community. Similar condition was also recorded for the bottom soil with pH values ranging from 2.70 -7.90. The total organic contents (TOC) varied from 0.18 - 2.00 with a mean value of 0.79% in the topsoil while a range of 0.40-1.26% with a mean value of 0.88% w^ras recorded in the bottom soil. Total nitrogen in the spill affected area varied from 0.02-2.48% (mean = 0.66%) and 0.03-2.45% (mean = 0.71%) for the topsoil and bottom soil respectively. Petroleum hydrocarbon levels varied from 19.76mg/kg (Tweni community) to 5922mg/kg (near the spill site) in the topsoil while it ranged from 18.24mg/kg - 4508mg/kg in the bottom soil. Menn TPH values in the top and bottom soil were higher than the control values, even though these values were below the intervention value of 5000mg/kg. Low concentration levels of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon (PAHs) were recorded in the topsoil (average - 1.25mg/kg) and bottom soil (average = 0.95 mg/kg). These values were below the PAHs Intervention value of 40.0mg/kg. BTEX were however absent in the soil as its concentration was below the detection limit (0.001mg/kg) of the analytical instrument. Heavy metal concentration levels varied from 8659 mg/kg - 20230mg/kg for Fe; 19.70 mg/kg - 180.24mg/kg for Zn; 3.80mg/kg - 29.00mg/kg for Cr; 0.60 mg/kg - 29.30mg/kg for Pb; 1.90mg/kg - 18.80.mg/kg for Cu; 0.10 mg/kg - 12.20mg/kg for Cd. Similarly, metals concentrations in the bottom soil varied from 8124mg/kg - 21250mg/kg, 23.30 mg/kg - 239.64mg/kg, 23.30mg/kg - 239.64mg/kg, 9.70-24.10mg/kg, 0.60-32.90mg/kg, 0.10 mg/kg- 15.30mg/kg, 2.90 mg/kg - 12.20mg/kg and 2.20 mg/kg - 13.10mg/kg for Fe, Zn, Cr, Pb, Cd, Ni and Cu respectively. Mercury, Barium and Vanadium were below their minimum detection limit of 0.001mg/kg in both topsoil and bottom soil. Metals concentrations were below their respective Intervention values and compared well with the respective mean values recorded at the control site. The total heterotrophic fungi (THB) and IT were of population densities across the sample station in the oil spill affected area. This is an indication of a viable community with capacity to mineralize organic matter, particularly the petroleum and petrogenic hydrocarbon in soil at various Depths.

24" Nembe - Cawthorne Channel Trunk Line (NCTL)

The pH values of soil samples varied from 3.0 - 7.8 (mean = 4.6) and 3.1 - 7.7 (mean=4.4) for the topsoil and bottom soil respectively. The observed acidic conditions at the spill site could be due to produced organic acids specifically fluvic and humic acids from microbial degrading processes of the petroleum hydrocarbon. Total organic carbon (TOC) levels varied from 0.05 - 4.95% and 0.04 4.94% in the topsoil

and bottom soil respectively. On the other hand, total nitrogen levels averaged 0.39% in the topsoil and 0.37% for the bottom soil. Total petroleum hydrocarbon levels in the topsoil ranged from 24.53ng/kg at Agneskiri. to 5201mg/kg at Botokiri. Furthermore, TPH concentrations in the bottom soil varied between 1.16mg/kg - 4801mg/kg with a mean value of 2035mg/kg. The TPH levels across the sampling stations, including the spill site, were below the Intervention value of 5000mg/kg. Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbon concentration levels ranged between 0.01 - 8.56mg/kg (mean 0.96mg/kg) and 0.01-3.14mg/kg (mean 0.64mg/kg) in the topsoil and bottom soil respectively. As reported at the control station. BTEX concentrations levels were absent across the sampling stations. Metals were recorded in concentrations below their respective Intervention values, across the sampling stations and compared favorably with values recorded at the control sites. The concentration abundance of heavy metals followed the same order, as Fe>Zn> Cr>Pb>Cu >Ni and Cd, in both top and bottom soils. Relatively high population densities of heterotrophs recorded in the soil is an indication of a viable community with capacity to mineralize organic matter. The hydrocarbon degraders (HUF and HUB) population densities were moderate and the ratios of HUF/TF and HUB. - THB population percentage were below 10%, indicating low degree petroleum hydrocarbon contamination in the soil layers of the study area.

VEGETATION

Four (4) habitat types i.e., freshwater, mangrove swamp, secondary' forest and modified grassland were identified in the study area. The vegetation in the area appears generally healthy, apart from the ones that were directly impacted by the spill, which are showing signs of stress.

FISHERIES

The spills did not seem to negatively affect the counts and diversity of phytoplankton, zooplankton and benthic invertebrates. The counts were higher at the alleged spill site compared to the background. Total petroleum hydrocarbon levels recorded were 0.589mg/kg, 2.548mg/kg and 4.238mg/kg in the muscular tissue of dead fishes in Santa Barbara. Botokiri and Odeama respectively. On the other hand, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons and BTEX were below the detection limit of 0.001mg/kg. Heavy metals were within background levels.

SOCIO- ECONOMICS

The socio-economic measurement framework formed was developed to determine the impacts of the Santa Barbra Well 1. Odeama Well 9 and Botokiri pipeline spill incidents. The framework included both direct and indirect indicators, which were reviewed with AITEO prior to initiating the socio-economic post impact report. The study identified socioeconomic impacts of the Santa Barbra Well 1, Odeama Well 9 and Botokiri pipeline spill incidents on employment, economy, occupation/source of livelihood, local employment, political impact, social impact, impact on cultural properties, and increase in social vices etc.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Surface water, sediment, soil, fish and vegetation within the vicinity of the oil spill sites, contained higher than background levels of TPH and therefore adjudged to be negatively impacted by the oil. But the average concentrations of hydrocarbons in the environment was lower than the intervention levels.

Recommendations

- Increase security surveillance and protection of oil installations
- Carry out frequent inspections and maintenance of oil installations
- Discourage illegal crude oil bunkering and artisanal refineries through awareness campaigns, sensitization and enforcement
- Carry out site delineation studies to determine the spatial extent of impact (Depths and spread), classify the scale of the spill into different categories (none, light, medium and heavy)
- Carry out site remediation and restoration of the medium and heavily impacted areas and/or monitor since the concentration of TPH in the soil and sediment is below the intervention limit of 5000 mg/kg.

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